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Elastic and ultrasonic properties of cadmium oxide

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The attenuation of ultrasonic waves has been estimated in rocksalt type (B1) and CsCl type (B2) structures of CdO at room temperature along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions. First of all, the higher order elastic constants have been computed using Born model with Mori and Hiki approach. Then, the second order elastic constants (SOECs) were applied to compute the mechanical constants such as shear modulus, Young's modulus, bulk modulus, tetragonal modulus, Poisson's ratio, Pugh's indicator for finding performance of CdO. Numerous physical quantities, such as ultrasonic velocity, Debye temperature, thermal conductivity, ultrasonic Gruneisen parameter and acoustic coupling constants have been determined for the chosen material. Finally, the attenuation of ultrasonic waves has been compared in B1 and B2 phases of CdO and discussed in correlation with available findings.

Keywords: Cadmium oxide, elastic constants, thermal properties, ultrasonic properties.

Introduction

Over the past few years metal oxides semiconductors have received enormous attention due to their interesting electrical and optical properties in several technologically challenging areas. One of the important semiconductor material is Cadmium Oxide (CdO). It is the transparent conductive oxides (TCOS) and are of high interest from industrial applications such as liquid crystal display (LCD), photoelectric devices, gas sensors, IR detectors, etc. It normally crystallizes into rock-salt structure (NaCl) under pressure¹⁻⁴. Sahoo *et al.*⁵ carried out Ab initio calculations on structural, elastic and dynamic stability of CdO at high pressures and concluded the transformation of CdO from B1 to B2 phase under hydrostatic pressure of ~87 GPa. Bhardwaj⁶ studied the structural and thermophysical properties of cadmium oxide using the Three-Body Potential (TBP) model. Jentys *et al.*⁷ studied the structural properties of CdO and CdS clusters in zeolite Y. The structural properties of CdO in the rock-salt (sodium chloride), cesium chloride *etc* was studied using first-principles

total energy calculations by Moreno *et al.*⁸. Dou *et al.*⁹ performed the experimental and theoretical investigation of the electronic structure of CdO using periodic Hartree-Fock and density functional methods. Piper *et al.*¹⁰ studied the electronic structure of single-crystal rocksalt CdO by soft x-ray spectroscopies and ab initio calculations.

In the present study, a computational approach has been followed for the investigation of ultrasonic attenuation in order to study the inherent properties of CdO. The Coulomb and Born-Mayer potentials model have been used to determine the elastic, mechanical and thermo-physical properties at room temperature. The van der Waals' forces of interaction have been neglected. To the best of our knowledge, no calculation has been done on the temperature dependent study of CdO using this model.

Theory

The temperature dependent elastic, mechanical and ultrasonic properties at room temperature have been

studied using simple Coulomb and Born-Mayer interionic potential models^{11,12}.

Elastic and Mechanical Properties : The evaluation of second- and third-order elastic constants (SOECs and TOECs) have been done using Mori and Hikki approach¹³.

The elastic constants computed helps in the evaluation of mechanical properties such as bulk modulus (B), Young's modulus (Y), shear modulus (S), Poisson's ratio (σ), Anisotropy (A) etc. using the approach followed in our previous work^{11,12}.

Ultrasonic Properties : The relation used for finding the ultrasonic velocities for waves propagating along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction for B1- and B2- type structured CdO is given in our previous work^{12,14}.

The ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction (Akhieser loss) for longitudinal and shear modes is given by Mason¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The SOECs and TOECs for B1 and B2 structures of CdO are computed at room temperature using the nearest neighbour distance (r_0) as 1.927 Å and hardness parameter (b) as 0.123 Å. The results obtained have been listed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Second and third elastic constants [$\text{in } \times 10^{11} \text{N/m}^2$] for CdO at room temperature.

CdO → SOEC/TOEC ↓	B1	B2
C_{11}	10.64	13.66
C_{12}	2.87	2.40
C_{44}	3.299	4.17
C_{111}	-160.22	-97.42
C_{112}	-11.87	-51.87
C_{123}	3.185	-59.83
C_{144}	5.459	-20.98
C_{166}	-13.44	-20.74
C_{456}	5.355	-49.67

Table 2 – Mechanical properties of CdO at 300K.

CdO	B(GPa)	Y(GPa)	G(GPa)	λ (GPa)	H(GPa)	C_p (GPa)	B/G	σ	A	P(gm/cm ³)	$G_{\{100\}}$	$G_{\{110\}}$
B1	54.6	86.9	35.2	31.17	6.23	-4.23	1.55	0.235	0.849	8.48	3.299	3.88
B2	61.5	112.4	47.0	30.1	9.55	-17.7	1.31	0.195	0.741	3.724	4.17	5.63

From Table 1, the elastic constant C_{11} represents elasticity in length and is found more in B2-CdO. A longitudinal strain at room temperature produces a change in C_{11} . The elastic constants C_{12} and C_{44} are related to the elasticity in shape, which is a shear constant. A transverse strain with temperature causes a change in shape without a change in volume. Therefore, from the values of C_{12} and C_{44} in B1 and B2-CdO these are less sensitive to temperature as compared to C_{11} .

Elastic modulus B , Y , G , σ , λ , μ , B/G and A are also calculated at room temperature using evaluated SOECs and are presented in Table 2. From Table 1 the value of $C_{44} > 0$ thus, the CdO is stable at room temperature according to Born stability criterion¹¹. The elastic constants helps in determining the response of the crystal to external forces. They play major role in determining the strength of the material. The single crystal shear moduli for the $\{100\}$ plane along the $[010]$ direction and for the $\{110\}$ plane along the $[110]$ direction are simply given by $G_{\{100\}} = C_{44}$ and $G_{\{110\}} = (C_{11} - C_{12})/2$, respectively. It is found that the shear moduli $G_{\{100\}}$ are always lower than $G_{\{110\}}$. The obtained ν values are less than the lower limit value of 0.25 which indicate that the interatomic forces in the B1 and B2-CdO are non-central forces. B/G for the chosen materials must be between 1.56 and 1.59 to be brittle in nature and thus, B1-CdO is more brittle from Table 2.

From Table 3, it is observed that the Debye average velocity (V_D) and Debye temperature (T_D) is highest for B2-CdO. The specific heat per unit volume (CV) and crystal energy density (E_0) have been computed from θ_D/T tables of AIP Hand book¹¹. The values for C_V in $10^7 \text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$ is equal to 1.58 and 0.67 for B1 and B2 CdO respectively. The value of E_0 is $3.43 \times 10^9 \text{J m}^{-3}$ for B1-CdO and $1.34 \times 10^9 \text{J m}^{-3}$ for B2-CdO. The acoustic coupling constants D_L and D_S (for longitudinal and shear waves) which assess the ability of thermal phonons to absorb energy from sound wave have been measured along $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions and is listed in Table 3. The total ultrasonic attenuation is higher for B1-CdO and the thermoelastic losses are more as compared to the values of B2-CdO in Table 3.

Table 3 – Ultrasonic velocities, thermal conductivity and D_L , D_S , αf^2 (in $10^{-16} \text{Nps}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$) along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction of CdO compounds at 300K.

CdO →	B1	B2
Parameters ↓		
V_L (10^3 m s^{-1})	3.54	6.06
V_S (10^3 m s^{-1})	1.97	3.34
V_D (10^3 m s^{-1})	2.196	3.728
T_D (K)	281	363
K ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	0.917	0.549
D_L	13.99	8.95
D_S	1.054	19.63
$(\alpha f^2)_L$	6.01	0.336
$(\alpha f^2)_S$	1.313	2.184
$(\alpha f^2)_{th}$	0.021	0.002
$(\alpha f^2)_{Total}$	7.345	2.522
τ_s (10^{-14}s)	3.59	1.75

Conclusion

On the basis of above discussion following point can be drawn:

- B1-CdO is more brittle in nature as compared to B2-CdO.
- Anisotropic factor, A is found to be smaller than unity for B1 and B2 CdO. So these are completely anisotropic materials.
- Thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time plays an important role for total at-tenuation in these materials and is higher for B1-CdO.
- The elastic, mechanical, thermal and ultrasonic properties of CdO may be used for further investigation and in the manufacturing industries.

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